

THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE STUDY OF EMPATHIC ABILITIES IN MODERN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH

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Abstract. Today, in the era of advanced information technologies, live communication between people, especially young people, is decreasing, and the form of manifestation of empathic relations is changing. Studying the psychological causes of empathic relationships, determining the factors and conditions that lead to the formation of empathy, and conducting psychoprophylactic and psychocorrective work that increases the importance of locus of control in the development of volitional regulation is one of the urgent issues.

Key words: empathic ability, unexpected event, conversation, communication, specific empathy, universal human needs, emotional experience, appreciative attitudes, reflexive abilities.

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ЭМПАТИЧЕСКИХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯХ

Аннотация. Сегодня, в эпоху развитых информационных технологий, живое общение между людьми, особенно молодыми, сокращается, а формы проявления эмпатических отношений меняются. Изучение психологических причин эмпатических отношений, определение факторов и условий, приводящих к формированию эмпатии, проведение психопрофилактической и психокоррекционной работы, повышающей значимость локуса контроля в развитии волевой регуляции, является одной из актуальных проблем.

Ключевые слова: эмпатическая способность, неожиданное событие, разговор, общение, специфическая эмпатия, универсальные потребности человека, эмоциональное переживание, оценочные установки, рефлексивные способности.

The phenomenon of "empathic ability" as a psychological mechanism of human spiritual and moral development is recognized as one of the most interesting and relevant issues for modern psychology. Also, as a scientific problem, empathic ability falls within the scope of the general problems of personality formation, and without understanding it, it is unrealistic to talk about a person's spiritual and moral development and his compassionate attitude towards the plight of other people. Before we turn to the psychological aspects of the manifestation of empathic ability and empathic attitude, it seems most appropriate to clarify the circumstances surrounding the first use of the concept of "empathy" in science.

As a rule, the word "empathic ability" is defined in a narrow sense as sympathy, understanding the psychological state of other people, while in a broader context, it is understood as a person's irrational knowledge of the inner world of other people, as well as a person's emotional attitude to the experiences of others or as a social feeling inherent in oneself. The term "empathy" was first introduced into science by E. Titchener, who managed to generalize the ideas about "sympathy" developed in philosophical traditions with a number of scientific approaches to empathy. To date, many scientific theories and concepts have been developed in science aimed at scientifically substantiating the concept of empathy, and their analysis requires a specific approach to the problem. The explanation of empathy in connection with the possibilities of consciousness and the teachings of psychoanalysis was given by Z. Freud, K. G. Jung, K. R. Rogers, A. S. Rachman, K. T. Montag, K. K. Lamm, M. L. Hoffmann, J.E. Hakansson, A.P. Goldstein, L.S. Greenberg, M.H. Davis, C.D. Batson, G.T. Barrett-Lennard found its reflection in the studies of foreign authors. In psychoanalysis, empathy is defined by Z. Freud as "empathy is the transfer of emotional states to others", the process of transferring one's own motives, feelings and thoughts as a means of protection, presenting them to other people. Even the subject himself may be unaware of this.

Empathy is an "unexpected event." The psychoanalytic approach is a set of scientific ideas that is of particular importance in the system of scientific approaches to the study of the specifics of the manifestation of empathic abilities and empathy as a psychic phenomenon. In 1905, Z. Freud was one of the first to define the concept of empathy: "We take into account the mental state of the patient, put ourselves in that position, and I try to understand the patient by comparing his condition with my own." Thus, understanding the state of the patient or feeling that state in oneself is an empathetic attitude or showing sympathy and caring for others, which is reflected in the ability to understand. K.G. Jung defines the essence of empathy as the search for "subjective content" from an object: "Since the essence of empathy consists in the projection of subjective content, the unconscious action preceding it must have the opposite property, that is, it is a process of restoring the effectiveness of the object. K.G. Jung interprets empathy as a mechanism of extroversion, adaptation, and protection.

Thus, empathy is a type of cognitive process, the characteristic of which is that with the help of emotion, some important psychological properties are absorbed into the object, and thus the object is introspected. There are various definitions and scientific approaches to the problems of empathy, which are manifested in emotional empathy, cognitive empathy, and predicative empathy, which are based on the motor and affective reactions of another person. As a special form of empathy, cognitive empathy stands out.

According to I. Bauer, three aspects of empathic experience are distinguished:

1) a clear understanding of the feelings, thoughts, needs of communication partners, the predominance of the moral and aesthetic level;

2) an “emotional attitude” to the events happening around;

3) a rational evaluation criterion and a state of moral reflection. D. Golman, as a specialist, associates empathy with “emotional intelligence”, although he is somewhat skeptical about the reasons for its origin, describing it as a natural state of affairs, and some disagreement in the literature about the definition of empathy. In client-centered psychotherapy, the concept of empathy is interpreted as “specific empathy” and the ability to penetrate the patient’s inner world. Researcher P.A. Miller, in his scientific approach, considers the development of empathy to be the formation of “universal human needs.” That is, it is the result of psychologists’ observation of the interaction between mother and child, although concepts such as “conversation” (W. Stern) and “mutual warmth” are also closely related to empathy.

As A.P. Vasilkova writes in her next scientific article, people with a high level of empathy are considered to have well-developed qualities such as softness, benevolence, politeness, and emotionality. According to the author, people with well-developed empathic abilities are distinguished from others by the following qualities:

attention;

care for others;

the ability to quickly find a solution in communication and interpersonal relationships;

the predominance of democratic and altruistic strategies in interpersonal interaction;

sensitivity to the non-verbal behavior of another person;

sensitivity to social emotions and moral feelings;

high sensitivity to human values and official norms of behavior and social tolerance.

Therefore, developing empathic abilities in a person from childhood, using psychological training, games to shape them, and creating new, advanced psychodiagnostic tests and methodologies to assess the level of empathy are considered one of the most promising tasks for modern psychology. In the field of psychology, a number of scientific approaches that study the development of empathic abilities and the trait of empathy have been distinguished, most of which are scientifically substantiated through the process of communication, the educational process, and pedagogical activity. For example, the study of the emotional interaction of educational participants, their characteristics, cannot be separated from the study of empathy, that is, sympathy for success and failure, sensitivity to the emotional state of others, positive interpersonal influence, and the crucial role it plays in shaping positive relationships between teachers and students.

In addition, according to M.L. Hoffman, the lack of empathetic relationships between people leads to a number of behaviors in the form of aggression, violence, bullying, and deviant

behavior. Therefore, in modern educational practice, the development of empathic abilities from preschool age, teaching children to be compassionate and cooperative, is considered one of the most important pedagogical and psychological tasks. With these thoughts, the author takes into account the high role of the educational institution in this matter. Based on the content of the theoretical approaches analyzed above, the following conclusions can be drawn: the issue of multifaceted empathic abilities is explained by foreign psychologists in the form of psychoanalytic, communicative skills, the ability to make an identification assessment in interpersonal relationships, the ability to have emotional experience, appreciative attitudes, and reflexive abilities. However, modern psychology feels the need for new, advanced research on this issue. And it would not be wrong to say that there is a great need for large-scale research in this regard in the local environment:

While the phenomenon of empathy is, on the one hand, a general psychological problem, on the other hand, it is considered a scientific category with a high socio-psychological status.

Because the empathic attitude expressed by one person towards another can later be recognized as the most important international, interethnic value. That is, high human qualities such as helping the needy on a global scale, providing selfless assistance, being sympathetic to difficult situations, and also caring from the heart are among them.

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